

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PREVALENCE OF GYNECOLOGICAL FINDINGS DISCOVERED DURING
WELL EXAMINATIONS FOR WOMEN 40 AND OVER

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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ABSTRACT

The concept of an annual well woman examination (WWE) has been established as a standard practice since cervical cancer screening was initiated in the United States. Recent changes in screening recommendations for cervical cancer screening have led some to question the utility of the annual WWE. The objectives for this study were to determine the prevalence of gynecological conditions discovered during a routine WWE and to establish the frequency of and describe the interventions employed relative to those findings.

Electronic medical records for women aged 40 and over presenting to the gynecology clinic at the Los Angeles County/University of Southern California Medical Center for a WWE were examined for a 6-month time period. Two hundred seventy-nine charts were reviewed. IBM SPSS version 22 was used to analyze the data. The level of significance was set at $p = .05$.

Fifty-five percent of women who presented for a WWE were found to have new gynecological findings; 45% of women had no new findings. There were no significant differences in terms of sample characteristics between the two groups. The mean age of the sample was 51.4 years, the mean body mass index was 30.9, and the majority of the women were Hispanic (82%) and Spanish speaking (70%). The most prevalent findings were pelvic organ prolapse (16%), abnormal uterine bleeding (13%), and pelvic masses

(12%). Fifty-two percent of women with findings required further diagnostic workup, 42% required prescriptive intervention, and 44% required educational intervention.

With the introduction of the human papillomavirus vaccine, the guidelines for cervical cancer screening will most likely be changing again in the near future. Further research is needed with different age groups and settings to determine the efficacy and the optimal interval for such examinations.

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BACKGROUND

The concept of an annual well woman examination (WWE) has been established as a standard practice since cervical cancer screening was initiated in the United States. As part of the WWE, a pelvic examination, cervical cancer screening, clinical breast examination, and mammography for women 40 and over have been the standard. Recent changes in screening recommendations for cervical cancer screening have led some to question the utility of the annual WWE. Some of the conditions that are evaluated during an annual well woman visit by history are abnormal uterine bleeding, urinary incontinence, and evaluation of peri and postmenopausal changes such as vasomotor symptoms and mood swings. These conditions are not specifically part of a pelvic examination but are evaluated during an annual WWE. Some of the conditions that are discovered during physical examination are pelvic masses such as uterine fibroids, atrophic vaginitis, pelvic organ prolapse, and vulvar lesions such as lichen sclerosus. For the purposes of this project, the utility of routine WWEs and pelvic examinations were evaluated. The evaluation of breast examinations and mammography is beyond the scope of this paper.

Background and Problem Statement

The evidence in the professional literature severely lacks any studies that investigate whether gynecological conditions are discovered during routine WWE and, if found, whether interventions are planned based on the findings. Among the experts, conflicting opinions leave clinicians wondering whether or not pelvic examinations are necessary. Throughout this paper, it will be understood that a reference to a WWE is inclusive of both the pelvic examination and gynecologic history. Some of the areas that

will be discussed are (a) current guidelines for cancer screening, (b) current evidence that describes routine pelvic examinations, (c) evidence that describes the interval for pelvic examinations, and (d) evidence that describes gynecologic health problems. This evidence is used to answer this Doctorate of Nursing Practice inquiry question: Are there benefits to doing routine WWEs in women over 40 other than completion of cervical cancer screening?

In 2009, the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology recommended cervical cancer screening beginning at age 21 every 2 years until age 29 and then every 3 years beginning at age 30 until ages 65-70 (Kauffman, Griffin, Lund, & Tullar, 2013). In 2012, the American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology along with the American Cancer Society and the American Society of Clinical Pathology revised the guidelines for cervical cancer screening and management of abnormal screening tests. The guidelines now recommend that cervical cancer screening begin at age 21. For women ages 21-29, it should be done every 3 years. Women aged 30-64 should be receiving a pap test, with human papillomavirus (HPV) testing every 5 years (Saslow et al., 2012).

These new guidelines lead those in the field to question the efficacy of a routine WWE (Kauffman et al., 2013). Historically, pelvic examinations were done on an annual basis simply because cervical cancer screening was recommended to be done annually. The new guidelines drastically change the interval that cervical cancer screening is recommended, so that leads many health care providers to question the interval needed for routine WWEs and the need for pelvic examinations in women after having a hysterectomy (Kauffman et al., 2013; Stormo, Cooper, Hawkins, & Saraiya, 2012).

In the absence of clear evidence regarding routine pelvic examinations, there are diametrically opposing views among the experts. The American College of Physicians recommended against routine pelvic examinations, citing that they found no evidence to support that routine pelvic examinations have any benefit and that it incurs substantial costs by leading to unnecessary procedures and anxiety (Bloomfield et al., 2014). The American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology (2009) recommended annual pelvic examinations for women beginning at age 21 as a routine part of preventive care even if they do not need cervical cancer screening.

There is a paucity of evidence for the intervals at which pelvic examinations are needed in the absence of cervical cancer screening or even if there is a benefit to such examinations. Most of the evidence in the literature addresses routine pelvic examinations as they pertain to detecting ovarian cancer. No articles were found that addressed the utility of a WWE to detect common gynecologic conditions.

As women age, they face a myriad of changes to their bodies, some that are apparent in face-to-face encounters and others that require close physical examination. Menopause, parity, overweight, and obesity all contribute to different effects on the pelvic floor muscles, such as pelvic organ prolapse and urinary incontinence. Atrophic vaginitis, lichen sclerosus, and dyspareunia can all lead to body image distortion, decreased sexual response, and social isolation (Haefner et al., 2014; Lowder, Ghetti, Nikolajski, Oliphant, & Zyczynski, 2011). The identification of these effects of aging and parity are some of the challenges faced by providers as they conduct a routine WWE.

Pelvic organ prolapse, atrophic vaginitis, and urinary incontinence are all examples of conditions that are part of the aging process or the result of normal

pregnancy. These are conditions that can benefit from early identification and basic interventions such as education, weight reduction/lifestyle changes, or topical estrogen (Braekken, Majida, Engh, & Bo, 2010; Long et al., 2006). No studies were found that researched the discovery of these conditions during a routine WWE. Although the evidence for cervical cancer screening is well-documented and the current guidelines have been well-researched, there is a void in the evidence that either supports or refutes the need for routine pelvic examination (Kauffman et al., 2013).

Purpose and Objectives

The purpose of this study was to contribute to the body of knowledge upon which the current practice of routine pelvic examinations is based. This was accomplished by evaluating the prevalence of new gynecologic conditions and interventions identified during a WWE among women 40 and over at an urban teaching medical center with associated specialty ambulatory clinics. This study included women presenting to the gynecology clinic for the purpose of a WWE.

The American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology has recently changed the guidelines for the interval of cytological screening for cervical cancer. Previously screenings were conducted annually. The American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology now recommends a pap smear every 5 years concurrent with HPV testing for women over 30. This has called into question the practice of routine annual pelvic examinations for women. The opinions of physicians regarding routine pelvic examinations of women have been explored in several studies, but they did not include the prevalence of gynecologic conditions discovered in such examinations (Henderson et al., 2013; Stormo et al., 2012). In point of fact, no studies were found

within the last 5 years that have investigated the prevalence of gynecological conditions discovered during a routine WWE.

The objectives for this project were as follows:

- To determine the prevalence of new gynecological conditions discovered during a routine WWE.
- To describe the interventions prescribed and establish their frequency.
- To disseminate the findings of the study to the health care community in order to stimulate new research into the utility and cost effectiveness of routine pelvic examinations for women 40 and over.
- To utilize this evidence to articulate to colleagues, patients, and administrators the reasons for performing routine pelvic examinations and a gynecologic history for asymptomatic women 40 and over.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

PubMed, CINAHL Plus with Full Text, MEDLINE, and Cochrane Library were searched using the search terms *pelvic organ prolapse, atrophic vaginitis, fibroids, abnormal uterine bleeding, dysmenorrhea, screening pelvic examinations, lichen sclerosus, menopause, and perimenopausal symptoms*. A total of 2,763 articles were selected. Those articles in English within the last 5 years were reviewed.

Articles that were concerned primarily with surgical interventions, postoperative complications, pregnancy, cytological identification, or adolescence were excluded. Reference lists of the American College of Physicians and the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology and clinical guidelines were also hand searched. A total of 59 articles were read and synthesized. Conditions that are closely related such as pelvic organ prolapse and urinary incontinence are discussed together.

The practice of an annual WWE has long been part of preventive gynecological care and considered a necessary part of women's routine health maintenance, but it now warrants investigation into its optimal interval (Kauffman et al., 2013). Recent changes in cervical cancer screening guidelines have brought to light the argument that annual routine pelvic examinations may not be necessary and, in fact, are believed by some to be detrimental by leading to unnecessary workups and anxiety (Bloomfield et al., 2014). To date, there have been no studies that have examined exactly what conditions are being investigated and diagnosed in those examinations. This writer began a literature search by exploring the current clinical guidelines and expert opinions available. The evidence was reviewed in each of these additional areas: routine pelvic examinations, pelvic organ prolapse, abnormal uterine bleeding, atrophic vaginitis, uterine fibroids, urinary

incontinence, vulvar lesions, dyspareunia, lichen sclerosus, sexual function menopausal, and perimenopausal symptoms. These conditions are inextricably linked to quality of life issues that women face as they age (Stiles, Redmer, Paddock, & Schragger, 2012). The literature review concludes with a discussion of the current gap in the evidence that exists relative to gynecological findings on routine pelvic exams of women 40 and over.

Guidelines and Opinions

Bloomfield et al. (2014) conducted a systematic review of the literature in order to evaluate the harm versus benefits and diagnostic accuracy of routine pelvic examinations of asymptomatic women. This review included 32 primary data studies and a total of 52 articles. The authors concluded that the studies reporting harm generally were of poor quality. Three studies examined the positive predictive value of screening for ovarian cancer with pelvic examination to be from 0% to 3.6%. Fifteen of the studies were investigations of the harm resulting from pelvic examinations. Nine studies examined the history of sexual violence as a predictor of pelvic examination experience. No studies were identified that evaluated morbidity or mortality of any gynecological conditions or any other types of cancer other than as a screening for ovarian cancer. Most authors focused on the bimanual portion of the pelvic examination (Grover & Quinn, 1995; Henderson et al., 2013) and its use in detecting ovarian cancer (Bloomfield et al., 2014; Qaseem et al., 2014). In contrast to the recommendations of Bloomfield et al. (2014) and thus the American College of Physicians, the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology (2009) recommended annual pelvic examinations whether or not cervical cancer screening was indicated.

The two studies that examined physicians' beliefs and attitudes regarding routine pelvic examinations (Henderson et al., 2013; Stormo et al., 2012) utilized a survey for physicians to complete by mail and online, respectively. Henderson et al. (2013) examined only the beliefs of obstetrician-gynecologists (OB/GYNs), and Stormo et al. (2012) surveyed OB/GYNs, internists, and family/general practitioners. Neither study found an agreement of the reasons or utility of such examinations, and neither study included any mid-level providers. Implementation of the new American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology guidelines has caused other practitioner groups to question the efficacy of the routine annual pelvic examination and call for a demonstration of evidence that either supports continuation of the practice or calls for its discontinuation (Kauffman et al., 2013).

Lichen Sclerosus

Lichen sclerosus is a chronic inflammatory condition of the skin that can affect the vulva and often results in significant disfiguration and discomfort. Several authors recognized that lichen sclerosus, pelvic organ prolapse, and atrophic vaginitis affect sexual function and quality of life (Haefner et al., 2014; Long et al., 2006; Lowder et al., 2011). Haefner et al. (2014) found in their case control study that women with lichen sclerosus were not only less sexually active than the control group, they also reported sexual activity less satisfying. Lowder et al. (2011), in their qualitative study, reported the themes of *feeling less attractive* and *avoiding intimacy* in women with lichen sclerosus.

Perimenopausal and Postmenopausal Symptoms and Atrophic Vaginitis

Hot flashes and night sweats (together referred to as vasomotor symptoms) affect approximately 40% of postmenopausal women. These symptoms affect quality of life by interfering with sleep, work, mood, and daily life (Kauffman et al., 2013). In a randomized trial of 110 postmenopausal and late perimenopausal women, the treatment group ($n = 57$) received mindfulness training in order to reduce the urgency of thoughts and affective states. The wait list control group ($n = 53$) were offered free participation in the mindfulness training program after the final study assessments. The authors reported a decrease in the mean bothersomeness score of 14.77% in the treatment group versus a 6.79% decrease in the control group. They also reported a 44.56% reduction of hotflash intensity in the treatment group versus 26.97% for the control group at 20 weeks (Carmody et al., 2011).

Usual treatment for vasomotor symptoms of menopause has been estrogen therapy. Some women may be unable to take estrogen therapy or are apprehensive about the risks of estrogen therapy. Three hundred and thirty-nine postmenopausal and perimenopausal women were randomized in a double-blinded study and were treated with low dose estradiol, venlafaxine XR (a serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor), or a placebo. At week 8, vasomotor symptom frequency decreased by 53% with estradiol, 48% with venlafaxine, and 29% with the placebo (Joffe et al., 2014).

Atrophic vaginitis was also found to negatively impact the sexual health and quality of life for postmenopausal women and their partners (Ratner, Erekson, Minkin, & Foran-Tuller, 2011). Approximately 25%-50% of postmenopausal women also

experienced vulvovaginal atrophy, which leads to dyspareunia, vulvovaginal irritation, soreness, itching, and burning sensations.

Pelvic Organ Prolapse and Urinary Incontinence

Using a U.S. claims and encounters database, the lifetime risk of surgery for pelvic organ prolapse or urinary stress incontinence was estimated to be 20% of women in the United States by the age of 80 (Wu, Matthews, Conover, Pate, & Funk, 2014). In a study of 504 women in Lebanon, 49.8% were found to have significant pelvic organ prolapse (Awwad, Sayegh, Yeretian, & Deeb, 2012). Risk factors for pelvic organ prolapse include a body mass index (BMI) greater than 24kg/m², multiparity, and increased age. Urinary symptoms, bulging, and pelvic heaviness were found to be predictors of pelvic organ prolapse (Awwad et al., 2012). Vaginal descensus, 0.5 cm distal to the hymen, was found to be a predictor of symptoms of protrusion and bulging symptoms (Gutman, Ford, Quiroz, Shippey, & Handa, 2008). In one retrospective study of 382 women seen for urinary incontinence, 62% were postmenopausal, 7% were using systemic estrogen replacement, and 6% were using topical estrogen (Trutnovsky, Rojas, Mann, & Dietz, 2014). The researchers also found topical estrogen to be useful in bladder overactivity (Trutnovsky et. al 2014). Braekken et al. (2010) found in their assessor-blinded randomized controlled trial of 109 women improvement of symptoms and improvement in degree of descent after a 6-month pelvic floor muscle training program. Using the Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification score system, the researchers reported significant improvement in scores for bladder ($p < 0.001$) and for rectum ($p = 0.02$) and reduced frequency and bother of symptoms with pelvic floor muscle training.

Abnormal Uterine Bleeding and Uterine Fibroids

Abnormal uterine bleeding is not a physical finding assessed in a pelvic examination, but it is assessed through taking a thorough menstrual history during the annual WWE. Women in some cultures may not perceive there is a problem until prolonged severe bleeding occurs and may not present for care until urgent investigation is needed (Munro, Heikinheimo, Haththotuwa, Tank, & Fraser, 2011). An association of abnormal uterine bleeding and obesity was reported in an observational case study in 20 women with a mean BMI of 32.63 (Nouri, Tavakkolian, & Mousavi, 2014).

Uterine fibroids are easily found during a routine WWE. The estimated direct cost of uterine fibroids annually in the United States is \$4.1 billion to \$9.4 billion, with an additional estimated cost of lost work of \$1.5 to \$17.2 billion (Cardozo et al., 2012). Predisposing factors for uterine fibroids include African ancestry, age, nulliparity, and obesity (Segars et al., 2014).

Sexual Function and Dyspareunia

In their literature review, Ratner et al. (2011) found little published evidence on interventions for sexual dysfunction in the elderly despite its prevalence. In a randomized comparative investigation of 57 women, Long et al. (2006) reported greater improvement of vaginal vascularization and a greater decrease in symptoms with topical estrogen cream over oral estrogen therapy. In the Cochrane review of 27 studies, which included 16,393 participants, Nastri et al. (2013) reported a moderate increase in sexual function with oral estrogen and combination estrogen/progesterone therapy.

In a randomized controlled trial of 245 women, pelvic floor muscle training was compared to circular muscle exercises using the Paula method (contracting and relaxing

other circular muscles in other areas of the body; Liebergall-Wischnitzer et al., 2012). A significant improvement was reported in quality of life index, 1-hour pad test, and sexual function in both the pelvic floor muscle training and Paula method groups. The authors reported a mean sexual function score improvement after intervention with the Paula method ($p = 0.012$) and with the pelvic floor muscle training ($p = 0.054$). Improvement was reported in leakage (pad test; $p \leq 0.001$ for the Paula method and $p \leq 0.001$ for the pelvic floor muscle training group) and quality of life score ($p \leq 0.001$ for the Paula method and $p \leq 0.01$ for the pelvic floor muscle training; Liebergall-Wischnitzer et al., 2012).

Health Care Costs

Although investigation into the cost benefits of cervical cancer prevention is documented, the cost benefit analyses of pelvic examinations is not found in the current literature. The cost of preventive and health promotion screening is clearly a factor in the journey to reduce health care costs and must continue to be investigated. The Markov health state transition model was used to compare screening strategies of primary HPV testing with HPV and pap smear cotesting and demonstrated that primary HPV testing could potentially lead to as many as 2,141 more invasive cervical cancer cases and 2,041 cervical cancer deaths (Felix et al., 2016). Cotesting yielded a savings of \$39 million and demonstrated greater effectiveness at a lower cost than HPV testing alone (Felix et al., 2016). Seto, Marra, Raymakers, and Marra (2012) conducted a systematic review of 29 articles that investigated the cost benefits of HPV vaccination programs and found the evidence to consistently show HPV vaccination to have a substantial impact on the epidemiology of HPV disease.

The estimated annual cost of routine cervical cancer screening and follow-up is approximately \$6.6 billion; approximately \$0.4 billion is spent annually on cervical cancer and \$0.3 billion is spent on genital warts. The National Breast and Cervical Cancer Early Detection Program estimates the cost of cervical cancer screening to be \$75 per visit (Chesson et al., 2012). The lifetime risk of surgery of pelvic organ prolapse or incontinence was found to be 20% (Wu, Matthews, et al., 2014). The estimated cost of a hysterectomy ranges from \$6,805 to \$11,538 per case (Cardozo et al., 2012).

Evidence Gap

No studies were found that researched the usefulness of the annual WWE to detect gynecological conditions other than as a screening for cancer (Bloomfield et al., 2014; Qaseem et al., 2014; Stewart & Thistlewaite, 2006). Several authors documented the prevalence and financial cost of the gynecological conditions that have been discussed (Bond & Horton, 2010; Haefner et al., 2014; Lowder et al., 2011). Many more studies have reported the impact of these same gynecological conditions on quality of life and sexual function for women as they age (Bond & Horton, 2010; Haefner et al., 2014; Lowder et al., 2011). To date, there have been no investigations into whether these gynecological conditions are being discovered during a routine WWE.

Although the annual pelvic examination has been a well-established practice in gynecology offices across the country, the reasons for such examinations are unclear and not based on evidence (Awwad et al., 2012; Cardozo et al., 2012; Wu, Matthews, et al., 2014). Gynecological conditions that affect women as they age can negatively affect their quality of life; many of the effects of these conditions can be reduced with early detection and prompt interventions. Routine examination is clearly needed at regular

intervals, but the optimal interval for such examinations for women as they age has yet to be established. According to Kauffman et al. (2013), “If a net benefit can be demonstrated, physicians and patients can be comforted. If not the practice of annual pelvic exam should be eliminated” (p. 320).

Conceptual Framework

The first nursing theory, called environmental theory, was developed by Florence Nightingale. The focal point of environmental theory was the individual’s health, which was promoted by strengthening the individual’s healing forces and creating a beneficial environment (Torres, 1986). Nursing theory provides articulation to demonstrate systematic thinking and professional convictions that distinguish nurses as independent health care providers (Moran, Burson, & Conrad, 2014). Theory is utilized to provide a methodical way to view phenomena. For this proposed project, the three levels of prevention (Leavell & Clark, 1953) are utilized as a conceptual framework to explore the concepts involved in researching routine gynecologic examinations of women 40 and over (Figure 1).

The three levels of prevention framework by Leavell and Clark was developed in the late 1940s. This framework has been widely used by public health agencies and has been adopted by nursing, medicine, and other allied health professionals (Katz & Ather, 2009). Leavell and Clark (1965) asserted preventive measures are most effective when applied to individuals who are either unaffected or those who are in the early stages and still asymptomatic. “Preventive medicine is the science and art of preventing disease, prolonging life and promoting physical and mental health and efficiency” (Leavell & Clark, 1965, p. 11).

Figure 1. Three levels of prevention.

The natural history of disease involves many factors, some of which are interacting long before the person has become involved. The preliminary interaction of causative factors with the person before the onset of the disease or condition is termed prepathogenesis. The first interaction between the disease provoking stimuli and the person who will be affected, leading to the resulting changes in form and function, is termed pathogenesis. The person interacts with the stimulus, which results in tissue changes or altered reactions. Prevention at any level of intervention depends on the knowledge of causative factors and the ease at which they may be intercepted or counteracted (Leavell & Clark, 1965).

Primary prevention refers to those interventions that target the prevention of disease and conditions by investigating the presence of and subsequent elimination or

reduction of risk factors identified (Katz & Ather, 2009). Examples of interventions relevant to this project include calculation of BMI to assess obesity risk and implement weight reduction programs, implementation of a weight reduction program to reduce risk of pelvic organ prolapse, a careful evaluation of menstrual history to evaluate for abnormal bleeding and initiate further diagnostic testing as necessary, use of estrogen cream and personal lubricants to prevent dyspareunia in postmenopausal women, education on normal changes of menopause or of risk reduction and education for the prevention of sexually transmitted infections. *Secondary prevention* includes examination and screening activities that attempt to discover and interrupt the disease or condition before it becomes symptomatic (Katz & Ather, 2009). Examples of secondary prevention include cervical cancer screening and clinical breast exams with screening mammography. The secondary interventions under investigation in this study are identification of early stages of pelvic organ prolapse, evaluation of abnormal uterine bleeding, and identification of vulvar lesions before they become symptomatic such as in lichen sclerosus or vulvar dysplasia. Referrals or further diagnostic tests would follow positive findings. *Tertiary prevention* is aimed at ameliorating the sequelae of established disease and conditions. Examples of tertiary prevention include referrals for surgery for advanced stages of pelvic organ prolapse and referrals for treatment of vulvar, uterine, and cervical cancer.

The proper utilization of the three levels of prevention results in reducing health care spending by preventing and reducing the effects of disease. The framework is best used to direct interventions at the primary and secondary levels. Identifying risk factors and educating patients on the benefits of risk reduction are examples of primary

interventions, which form the foundation of the pyramid. The secondary level of prevention aims to detect conditions at an early stage, before the person becomes symptomatic, and provide prompt treatment, which prevents debilitating conditions. This forms the body of the pyramid, including screening tests and education on symptom reduction. In tertiary prevention, interventions are more extreme, the conditions are more advanced, and interventions are targeted at rehabilitation. Tertiary prevention would include surgical intervention for cervical cancer or advanced stages of pelvic organ prolapse and treatment of breast cancer. This forms the tip of the pyramid. The goal of the three levels of prevention is to practice at a higher level of care and involves looking ahead as well as treating the disease or condition that already exists (Leavell, 1953).

In a routine wellness examination, the provider may also have time to address quality of life issues such as dyspareunia and vaginal atrophy and issues related to sexual function (Stiles et al., 2012). The benefits of lifestyle modifications, diet, and exercise are less costly when intervening from the beginning stage of pelvic organ prolapse rather than in later stages in which surgery may be needed. Routine examinations of women are essential in each of the three levels of prevention.

Women will often delay routine health examinations based on time and financial considerations or based on their health beliefs and attitudes; less educated patients are often less likely to seek preventive care (Green, Johnson, & Yarborough, 2014; Hatchett, Hebert-Beirne, Tenfelde, Lavender, & Brubaker, 2011). A routine examination offers providers the opportunity to listen to the concerns of the patient and to discuss positive lifestyle modifications and utilize a collaborative, holistic approach with the patient. The relationship that can develop over time between patient and provider during routine

examinations can lead to early detection of health care concerns and enhance the patient's use of future preventive services (Green et al., 2104).

The goal of implementing any preventive medicine program is to discover conditions in the early stages in order to begin simple interventions before more drastic interventions are necessary. Leavell and Clark's three levels of prevention model demonstrates the different levels at which the interventions are directed. Small lifestyle changes can prevent more radical interventions from becoming necessary. A routine WWE has been utilized successfully to detect gynecological conditions that if undetected can lead to increased morbidity and mortality and decreased quality of life for women as they age.

The three levels of prevention conceptual model by Leavell and Clark was used to delineate the level of prevention that was employed by resident physicians and nurse practitioners conducting WWEs for a 6-month period. The data were collected from medical records using an author-developed tool to describe the levels of prevention used, the prevalence of gynecologic findings, and subsequent primary or secondary interventions implemented and identify those patients referred for further diagnostic workup or tertiary intervention. In summary, the three levels of prevention model was used to describe the gynecologic conditions being discovered by WWEs and the types of interventions used and establish the frequency with which those interventions were utilized.

METHODS

Setting

The Los Angeles County/University of Southern California (LAC/USC) Medical Center is a 600-bed teaching hospital and level 1 trauma center with ambulatory care clinics located in the city of Los Angeles, California. The gynecology clinic serves the residents of Los Angeles County for a variety of gynecological needs and primary well woman care. The LAC/USC Medical Center accepts Medi-Cal and Medicare and has an ability-to-pay program for indigent patients.

Audit Tool and Content Validity

The tool was developed by the author based on the study purpose and objectives and the literature and in consultation with faculty advisors. The audit tool was reviewed by five experts in the field for face and content validity. One of the experts was an attending physician of the gynecology department, one was the director of the women's health clinics, one was the attending physician of the uro-gynecology department, and two of the experts were women's health advanced practice nurse practitioners working in the gynecology department. Adjustments were made to the tool in response to feedback (Appendix A).

The tool consists of 25 columns; the first two columns contain the patient's assigned number and date of visit and the next columns contain BMI, age, and parity. The next two columns are ethnicity and language, with the categories of Asian, White, Black, Hispanic, and other under ethnicity and English, Spanish, Chinese, Korean, and other under language. The following columns are indicated as yes and no for pap smear and the conditions of decreased libido, pelvic organ prolapse, vulvovaginal atrophy,

vulvar lesions, vasomotor symptoms, mood swings, involuntary loss of urine, abnormal uterine bleeding, and dyspareunia. In order to indicate only new findings, pelvic masses contained the categories of yes, no, or history of. The column for genital lesions included Bartholin's gland cyst, vaginal cyst, cervical polyp, condyloma, other, and none. The column for primary prescription contained the categories of Premarin cream, hormone replacement therapy (HRT), other, and none. Primary education included Kegel's exercises, use of a personal lubricant, lifestyle changes, screening guidelines, wellness center, normal menstrual changes, hormone replacement/selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI), other, and none in its column. The column for secondary prescription contained anticholinergic/muscarinic antagonist, HRT/antidepressants, Premarin cream (for symptomatic atrophic vaginitis), pessary, other, and none. The secondary education column contained Kegel's exercises, herbal preparations/alternative therapies, other, and none. The diagnostics column contained the categories of endometrial biopsy, gonorrhea/chlamydia, wet mount, urine analysis/culture, vulvar biopsy, pelvic ultrasound, other, and none. Each row represented the data for one woman, which was collected on her WWE.

Three raters reviewed the same five charts and the results were reviewed for interrater reliability using percent agreement. The results of the interrater reliability indicated the raters agreed on their data 90% of the time.

Design

The design for this study was a simple descriptive design. A 6-month time period was identified from December 2014 to May 2015 and all electronic medical records (EMRs) of individuals who met the sample criteria were reviewed.

Sample and Data Collection Method

All EMRs were examined for women ($N = 279$) who presented for a WWE at the LAC/USC Medical Center within the previous 6 months to determine if there were new gynecological conditions discovered and interventions implemented as a result of the WWE. The EMR was searched and visits for all women 40 and over who had a WWE, annual exam, or routine exam or pap smear as a diagnosis were included. Women presenting for a specific gynecological problem as well as women who had recently been seen and were scheduled for a follow-up, preop, or postop visit were excluded.

Institutional Review Board Approvals

Human subjects protection determination expedited review was obtained from the LAC/USC Medical Center's Institutional Review Board (IRB) and from California State University, Los Angeles' IRB (Appendix B). Paper tracers of patient visits were obtained from health records management. Once a medical record was obtained and the visit status confirmed, the paper tracers were discarded in the secure shredding bin. The patient records were retrieved with no identifiers from the record other than the last four digits of the medical record number and the patient's age. Those identifiers were used to confirm that each patient visit for a WWE was included. All extracted data were kept in an encrypted file. No links between data and patients' identifying information were kept. The information gathered was reported in aggregate only and no individual patient information was kept. This project adhered to the regulations of the Health Insurance Portability and Protection Act (HIPPA) to protect the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants. To safeguard patient confidentiality and privacy, the facility and the

investigator established a limited data use agreement. A limited dataset containing limited patient information, as defined and allowed by HIPPA, was utilized.

Data Analysis

IBM SPSS version 22 was utilized for the analysis of the data. A level of significance of $p = .05$ was used. EMRs were examined for 279 women who presented for a WWE at the LAC/USC Medical Center for gynecological care within the 6-month period. The resulting data were described using simple descriptive statistics. Women who had one or more new gynecological conditions discovered in the WWE were compared with the overall number of women who received a WWE with no findings; independent samples t tests and chi-square tests were used to compare demographic data. The primary outcome of these analyses was to determine the prevalence rate of new gynecological conditions discovered as a result of a WWE, by history or examination, and describe the interventions planned.

FINDINGS

Sample Characteristics

Table 1 describes the characteristics of the sample. The mean age of the sample was 51.4 years, with a range of 40-70 years old. The mean BMI was 30.9, with a range of 18-72. The majority of the women were Hispanic (82%) and Spanish speaking (70%). The second largest group of women were White (5%) and 28% of the women spoke English as a first language.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Sample (N = 279)

	Mean (SD)	Mode (range)	Freq (valid %)
Age	51.4 (8.0)		
BMI	30.9 (7.0)		
Parity		3 (0-10)	
Ethnicity			
Asian			13 (4.7)
White			15 (5.4)
Black			13 (4.7)
Hispanic			230 (82.4)
Other			7 (2.5)
Unknown			1 (0.4)
Language			
English			77 (27.6)
Spanish			195 (69.9)
Chinese			4 (1.4)
Korean			1 (0.4)
Other			2 (0.7)
Any New Gynecological Conditions Identified During WWE			
Yes			153 (54.8)
1 new condition only			98 (64.1)
2 or more new conditions			55 (35.9)
No ^a			126 (45.2)

^a24 women had existing pelvic masses but were counted as not having a new condition identified in the WWE.

Comparison of Patients With and Without Findings

Of the 279 women sampled, 55% of the women had one or more new gynecological condition identified as a result of having a WWE. Forty-five percent of the women had no new conditions identified. Table 2 describes the two samples when they were divided according to the presence or absence of gynecological findings. The two groups were evaluated for significant differences using the independent samples *t* test for interval and ratio data. Overall, there were no significant differences in characteristics between the two groups when divided (see Table 2).

Table 2

Comparison of Demographic Characteristics of Patients With and Without Gynecological Conditions

	One or More Gynecological Yes (<i>n</i> = 153)		Conditions Identified No (<i>n</i> = 126)		<i>p</i>
	Mean (<i>SD</i>)	Freq (valid %)	Mean (<i>SD</i>)	Freq (valid %)	
Age	51.4 (8.4)		51.5 (7.6)		.95
BMI	30.7 (6.6)		31.1 (7.4)		.63
Parity					.75
0		21 (13.7)		25 (19.8)	
1		21 (13.7)		15 (11.9)	
2		33 (21.6)		25 (19.8)	
3		39 (25.5)		31 (24.6)	
4+		39 (25.5)		30 (23.8)	
Ethnicity ^a					.52
Asian		5 (3.4)		8 (6.5)	
White		10 (6.8)		5 (4.0)	
Black		7 (4.8)		6 (4.8)	
Hispanic		125 (85.0)		105 (84.7)	
Language ^b					.73
English		44 (29.1)		33 (27.3)	
Spanish		107 (70.9)		88 (72.7)	

^a*n* = 271 for this analysis.

^b*n* = 272 for this analysis.

Findings by History or Examination

Prevalence was calculated for those findings (cases/total sample*1,000) that were discovered by history and for those conditions discovered by physical examination.

Physical examination included physical inspection, speculum examination, bimanual examination, and palpation. Findings are summarized in Tables 3 and 4. The two most prevalent findings by history were abnormal vaginal bleeding (13%) and involuntary loss of urine (12%). The least reported finding was mood swings (0.7%). The three most prevalent findings resulting from the physical exam were pelvic organ prolapse (16%), pelvic masses (12%), and vulvovaginal atrophy (12%). The least prevalent finding by examination was a vaginal cyst (0.4%).

Table 3

Prevalence of New Gynecologic Findings Discovered by History or Examination

New Conditions Discovered by	Prevalence (per 1,000)	Percentage
History		
Abnormal uterine bleeding	129.0	12.9
Involuntary loss of urine	114.7	11.5
Vasomotor symptoms	39.4	3.9
Dyspareunia	35.8	3.6
Decreased libido	10.8	1.1
Mood swings/emotional lability	7.2	0.7
Examination		
Pelvic organ prolapse	164.9	16.5
Pelvic masses	121.9	12.2
Vulvovaginal atrophy	114.7	11.5
Genital lesions, overall	53.8	5.3
Vulvar lesions	21.5	2.2
Cervical polyp	14.3	1.4
Bartholin's gland cyst	7.2	0.7
Other	7.2	0.7
Vaginal cyst	3.6	0.4

Table 4

Prevalence Rates of New Gynecological Conditions Discovered

Conditions	<i>N</i>	Prevalence (per 1,000)
All new conditions	153	548.4
Pelvic organ prolapse	45	164.9
Abnormal uterine bleeding	36	129.0
Pelvic masses	34	121.9
Vulvovaginal atrophy	32	114.7
Involuntary loss of urine	32	114.7
Genital lesions, overall	15	53.8
Vulvar lesions	6	21.5
Cervical polyp	4	14.3
Bartholin's gland cyst	2	7.2
Other	2	7.2
Vaginal cyst	1	3.6
Vasomotor symptoms	11	39.4
Dyspareunia	10	35.8
Decreased libido	3	10.8
Mood swings/emotional lability	1	7.2

Prevalence Rates of Findings Overall

Fifty-five percent of women had new gynecological conditions discovered as a result of their WWE. When findings found through history and physical exam were combined, the most prevalent conditions discovered were pelvic organ prolapse (16%), abnormal uterine bleeding (13%), and pelvic masses (12%). Vulvovaginal atrophy and involuntary loss of urine were tied for fourth place (11%). The least reported finding was mood swings/emotional lability (0.7%). Of the genital lesions that were discovered as a result of the WWE, vulvar lesions were the most frequently reported (2%).

Description of Interventions

The objectives of this study were to investigate if new conditions were being discovered during the WWE and to determine the frequency of interventions. The interventions reported were based on the responses of the entire sample. Of the 279

women who received a WWE, 55% had new gynecological findings. The most frequently applied interventions in broad categories were diagnostic workup (50%), secondary prescription (27%), and primary education (25%; see Table 5).

Pelvic ultrasound, which is used for the evaluation of both abnormal uterine bleeding and pelvic masses, was the most reported diagnostic intervention (21%). The most frequently reported primary prescription was for Premarin cream (6%), and the most frequently reported primary education was on recommended screenings (5%). The most frequently reported secondary prescriptive intervention was in the other category (16%), which included iron supplementation for anemia and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatories for pelvic pain or dysmenorrhea. The most frequently reported secondary education was for Kegel's exercises (6%). Primary interventions (37%), such as examples given above, were utilized only slightly more often than secondary interventions (34%).

Referrals to other departments were necessary for 9% of patients and included primary care and breast clinic. Examples of reasons for referrals ranged from hernias, follow-up of elevated blood pressure, and a newly discovered breast mass. Twenty-four percent of patients were scheduled to return to the gynecology department for surgical follow-up or uro-gynecology clinic for follow-up. Conditions for which follow-up was necessary included abnormal uterine bleeding, urinary incontinence, and pelvic masses. Conditions for which interventions were implemented, but no follow-up was needed, included vaginal infections, early pelvic organ prolapse, and early vulvovaginal atrophy.

Table 5

Frequency of Interventions for All Patients

Type of Intervention	<i>N</i>	%
Primary Prescription		
Premarin cream	16	5.7
Other	8	2.9
HRT	3	1.1
Secondary Prescription		
Other	45	16.1
Anticholinergic	7	2.5
Premarin cream	6	2.2
HRT	4	1.4
Pessary	3	1.1
Education Primary		
Screening	15	5.4
Lifestyle changes	14	5.0
Kegel's	13	4.7
Normal menstrual changes	11	3.9
Other	10	3.6
HRT/SSRI	5	1.8
Wellness	5	1.8
Education primary—lubricant	2	0.7
Education Secondary		
Education secondary—Kegel's	17	6.2
Education secondary—other	12	4.3
Education secondary—herbal	1	0.4
Diagnostics		
Pelvic ultrasound	58	20.8
Diagnostics—endometrial biopsy	25	9.0
Diagnostics—other	24	8.6
Urinanalysis/Culture and sensitivity	22	7.9
Gonorrhea/Chlamydia	18	6.5
Wet mount	12	4.3
Vulvar biopsy	2	0.7
Referrals		
Gyn surg (follow-up)	58	20.8
Primary care	17	6.1
Urogyn	9	3.2
Referral—other	2	0.7
Breast mass	1	0.4
Referral—general surgery	1	0.4

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

The findings of this study indicated that women in this setting had new gynecological conditions discovered as a result of their WWE; 55% of the women seen had new conditions discovered. The most prevalent condition discovered was pelvic organ prolapse, which was discovered in 16% of those women seen in this time period. A comparison was made of those conditions that were discovered as a result of examination and those discovered as a result of the patient's history. Both of these are important components of the WWE. The most frequent conditions discovered by history were abnormal uterine bleeding (13%) and involuntary loss of urine (12%). The most prevalent conditions discovered as a result of pelvic examination were pelvic organ prolapse (16%) and pelvic masses (12%). The most frequent interventions that were employed as a result of a WWE were diagnostics (52%), secondary prescription (28%), and primary education (26%). The objectives of this study did not include a cost-benefit analysis of the interventions provided, so a precise net benefit cannot be determined. However, 76% of patients did not require gynecological follow-up, and the treatment was completed at that appointment. Six percent of the women were referred to primary care for the evaluation of conditions discovered, such as hypertension or diabetes, and 1% were referred to other disciplines for other nongynecological medical conditions that were discovered as a result of the WWE.

Comparison to the Literature

In this study, 55% of women who presented for a WWE had other new gynecological conditions discovered as a result. Sixteen percent of women had pelvic

organ prolapse discovered during their exam, and involuntary loss of urine was found to be 12%, which is consistent with Wu, Vaughan, et al. (2014) who found the prevalence rate of women with one or more types of pelvic organ prolapse to be 25% and with Nygaard et al. (2008) who found the prevalence of one or more pelvic floor disorders to be 23.7%. In this study, Kegel's exercises were utilized as a primary intervention for 4.7% of women and as a secondary intervention for 6.2% of women. Education on lifestyle changes were discussed with only 5% of women despite a mean BMI of 30.9. Braekken et al. (2010) found that 19% of the women with pelvic organ prolapse improved one Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification system stage after a 6-month period of pelvic floor muscle exercises. These findings indicate a potential for improvement of utilizing the opportunity in the WWE to discuss proactive changes to improve outcomes.

A possible explanation for the low percentage of women who received education on lifestyle changes could be that although diet and exercise was discussed, it was not documented. Another possibility is due to the large facility with various departments operating in a compartmentalized fashion, in which responsibility for care is presumed to be that of another department.

Simon, Nappi, Kingsberg, Maamari, and Brown (2014) found 58% of North American postmenopausal women with vaginal atrophy experienced vaginal discomfort and avoided intimacy and approximately 30% ceased being sexually active entirely due to vaginal discomfort. Approximately one third reported that they felt they were no longer sexually attractive. Twenty-nine percent reported improvement of intercourse after local estrogen therapy. Vulvovaginal atrophy was reported in 12% of the women in this study, with a mean age of 51, which is consistent with Ratner et al. (2011) who found

25%-50% of postmenopausal women to also have vulvovaginal atrophy. This study found 12% of women presenting for a WWE had vulvovaginal atrophy, and 8% received local estrogen therapy (Premarin cream). Only 0.7% received education on using a personal lubricant for intercourse.

In contrast to the current literature (Awwad et al., 2012; Wu, Matthews, et al., 2014), this study did not find a significant relationship between BMI, parity, and pelvic floor disorders. Some possible explanations for this include lack of uniformity in measurement of height and weight on which BMI was calculated and lack of uniformity in documentation of pelvic organ prolapse. Potential actions to minimize these problems in future studies could be to provide education to nursing staff on the importance of accurate height and weight for each patient in order to use the actual measurement of height and weight instead of patient self-report, which depends on patient recall and may be inaccurate, and to educate providers to use the same quantification system for documentation of pelvic organ prolapse.

Adequacy of Conceptual Framework

The use of Leavell and Clark's three levels of prevention as a conceptual framework enhanced the ability of the author to describe the interventions applied to women at their WWE. It also facilitated the understanding of the degree to which women were affected by these conditions. Primary interventions (37%) were utilized only slightly more often than secondary interventions (34%). This framework reinforces the differences in the stages in illness and health; however, some of the interventions overlap and can be used as either primary or secondary. While diagnostic workup is an intervention, it is categorized separately because until the results of the workup have been

obtained, the level of intervention is unknown. Interventions for a woman with abnormal uterine bleeding would include an endometrial biopsy and pelvic ultrasound, but the level of intervention is unknown until the results of the ordered tests are obtained. Possible diagnoses include uterine fibroids, endometrial cancer, hyperplasia, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, and endometrial polyp. The purpose of this study was not to consider the utility of each of the individual interventions but to describe if interventions were employed as a result of the WWE and establish their frequency.

Limitations

The limitations of this study are a single setting, with a primarily Hispanic and Spanish-speaking population, having limited resources and access to care; many of this underserved population may wait until they are symptomatic before coming in for routine examinations. The study was also conducted by a review of EMRs of multiple providers and relied on the documentation of those providers. Many times, a patient may not mention some of her concerns until the end of her visit and providers may provide education or a referral and not document it in the record. Some of the women had overlapping gynecological conditions and received multiple interventions, thus making it difficult to correlate specific interventions to a particular condition. This study did not explore mortality or harms associated with a WWE in this population.

CONCLUSIONS

Implications for Clinical Practice

The findings of this study support the American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology's position that an annual pelvic examination is an important part of preventive care for women. A thorough WWE by a skilled provider has the potential for discovering new gynecological conditions. The discovery of these conditions at an early stage can enhance the health and quality of life for women as they age. The WWE is an opportunity for proactive interventions such as education on lifestyle changes and pelvic floor muscle training. Education on lifestyle changes were used only 5% of the time, while the mean BMI was 31. This study highlights the need for increased attention to education, more directed histories aimed at improving communication on sexuality and emotional issues by providers and nurses, and the documentation of those interventions.

Implications for Future Research

With the introduction of the HPV vaccine, the guidelines for cervical cancer screening will most likely be revised again in the near future. The need to establish recommendations for pelvic examinations in the absence of cervical cancer screening based on evidence will become even more imperative. The discovery of new gynecological conditions in 55% of the women who presented for a WWE indicates that such examinations have the potential for preventing further progression of disease and enhancing the quality of life for women over 40. Future investigations could focus on further refinement of the investigation of interventions and their relationship to specific conditions. Further research is also needed with different age groups, patient populations, and settings to determine the efficacy, optimal interval, mortality, and harms

associated with such examinations. Further refinement of the investigation of interventions and their relationship to specific conditions could also be a focus of future research.

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APPENDIX B

INSTITUTIONAL BOARD APPROVALS

Hi Dr. Hughes and Cynthia,

I received your waiver of review W14-53 Cynthia Hughes/ Cynthia Sanchez "Prevalence of Gynecological findings of women 40 and over discovered during well woman examinations" on 6/16/15.

No further action is necessary.

Thanks,

Elia

ELIA AMARO, MSA

Research Support Services Coordinator

Office of Research and Development
California State University, Los Angeles
5151 State University Drive | Los Angeles, CA 90032
T 323.343.3798 | eamaro@calstatela.edu
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Cynthia Sanchez <_____>

Fw: Study Approval Notice Sent

1 message

Cynthia Sanchez <_____> Wed, Mar 30, 2016 at 12:44 PM

To: "_____" <_____>

From: istar@istar.usc.edu <istar@istar.usc.edu>

Sent: !Saturday, !June!6, !2015!8:08!AM

To: !Cynthia!Sanchez

Subject: !Study!Approval!NoBce!Sent

Proposal #HS-15-00333

University of Southern California Health Sciences Campus Institutional Review Board

LAC+USC Medical Center, General Hospital Suite 4700

1200 North State Street, Los Angeles, CA 90033

(323) 223-2340 phone

irb@usc.edu

Date: Jun 06, 2015, 08:07am

To: [Cynthia Sanchez, MSN](#)

Nurse Practitioner

OBSTETRICS & GYNECOLOGY

TITLE OF PROPOSAL:

Prevalence of Gynecological Findings of Women 40 and over discovered during Well Woman

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Examinations ([Gynecological findings on WWE](#))

Action Date: 06/06/15 Action Taken: Approved

Note: Your iStar application and attachments were reviewed on June 06, 2015.

The project was APPROVED.

Approval of your study will expire at the end of the day (midnight) on June 05, 2016.

The materials submitted and considered for review of this project included:

1. iStar Application, 06/03/15
2. Data Collection Form

This study was submitted for expedited review according to 45 CFR 46.110(b) (5).

In approving this research the IRB determined that all of the following were satisfied: (1) Risks to subjects are minimized: (i) by using procedures which are consistent with sound research design and which do not unnecessarily expose subjects to risk, and (ii) whenever appropriate, by using procedures already being performed on the subjects for diagnostic or treatment purposes. (2) Risks to subjects are reasonable in relation to anticipated benefits, if any, to subjects, and the importance of the knowledge that may reasonably be expected to result. In evaluating risks and benefits, only those risks and benefits that may result from the research are considered (as distinguished from risks and benefits of

therapies subjects would receive even if not participating in the research). (3) Selection of subjects is equitable (the purposes of the research and the setting in which the research will be conducted were taken into account). (4) Informed consent will be sought from each prospective subject or the subject's legally authorized representative. (5) Informed consent will be appropriately documented. (6) When appropriate, the research plan makes adequate provision for monitoring the data collected to ensure the safety of subjects. (7) When appropriate, there are adequate provisions to protect the privacy of subjects and to maintain the confidentiality of data.

As the Principal Investigator you are required to ensure that this research and the actions of all project personnel involved in conducting the study will conform with the research project and its modifications approved by the IRB, IRB Policies and Procedures, and applicable state laws. Failure to comply may result in suspension or termination of your research project, notification of appropriate governmental agencies by the IRB, and/or suspension of your freedom to present or publish results.

Any proposed changes in the research project must be submitted, reviewed and approved by the IRB before the change can be implemented. The only exception is a change necessary to eliminate apparent immediate hazards to the research subjects. In such a case, the IRB should be promptly informed of the change following its implementation for IRB review. You must inform the IRB immediately if you become aware of any violations of applicable state laws or IRB Policies and Procedures for the protection of human subjects. You are required to notify the IRB office in the event of any action by the sponsor, funding agency or FDA, including warnings, suspension or termination of your participation in this trial. You must maintain all required research records and recognize the IRB is authorized to inspect these records.

IRB approval is valid for a maximum period of one year with continuing review by the IRB required at least every year in order to maintain approval status. You may not enter subjects on the study before IRB approval or if IRB approval expires. In the latter case you must immediately contact the IRB to obtain permission to continue subjects on the trial. You must submit a Continuing Review Form sufficiently (one to two months) prior to your study expiration date to permit IRB review before the expiration date.

You must inform the IRB of any unanticipated adverse event or injury no later than ten (10) business days following the time it becomes known that a subject suffered an adverse event/injury. To report

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external or internal adverse events to the IRB, you must complete and submit the Reportable Event forms in iStar. Furthermore, you must inform the IRB immediately of any significant negative change in the risk/benefit relationship of the research as originally presented in the protocol and approved by the IRB.

INFORMED CONSENT

The request for a WAIVER OF INFORMED CONSENT is approved as iStar item 24 adequately documents that: (a) the research involves no more than minimal risk to the subjects; (b) the waiver or alteration will not adversely affect the rights and welfare of the subjects; (c) the research could not practicably be carried out without the waiver or

alteration; and (d) the subjects will be provided with additional pertinent information after participation (where appropriate).

HIPAA AUTHORIZATION

The request for a waiver of HIPAA Authorization is approved. The investigator has provided justification by specifically documenting the following: (1) The use or disclosure of protected health information involves no more than minimal risk to the privacy of individuals, based on, at least, the presence of the following elements: (a) There is an adequate plan to protect the identifiers from improper use and disclosure; (b) There is an adequate plan to destroy the identifiers at the earliest opportunity consistent with conduct of the research, unless there is a health or research justification for retaining the identifiers or such retention is otherwise required by law; and (c) There are adequate written assurances that the protected health information will not be reused or disclosed to any other person or entity, except as required by law, for authorized oversight of the research project, or for other research for which the use or disclosure of protected health information would be permitted by this subpart. (2) The research could not practicably be conducted without the waiver or alteration; and (3) The research could not practicably be conducted without access to and use of the protected health information.

You must use the data collection form submitted.

Attachments:

Approved Documents: [view](#)

This is an auto-generated email. Please do not respond directly to this message using the "reply" address. A response sent in this manner cannot be answered. If you have further questions, please contact your IRB Administrator or IRB/CCI office.

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